

Phospholipase C :
IP₃/DAG Pathway

گروه: هلیاسینامهر - پریناز رفیعی - سالار کی قبادی

- PHOSPHOLIPASE C (PLC) ENZYMES CONVERT PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL-4,5-BISPHOSPHATE INTO THE SECOND MESSENGERS DIACYLGLYCEROL AND INOSITOL-1,4,5-TRIPHOSPHATE. THE PRODUCTION OF THESE MOLECULES PROMOTES THE RELEASE OF INTRACELLULAR CALCIUM AND ACTIVATION OF PROTEIN KINASE C
- WHICH RESULTS IN PROFOUND CELLULAR CHANGES.

THIS PATHWAY IS SEEN DOWNSTREAM TO THE Gq PROTEIN UNDER RESTING STATE THE TRIMER OF A, B, AND Y IS BOUND TO THE RECEPTOR AND A SUBUNIT IS BOUND TO GDP

THE BINDING OF A LIGAND WITH THE RECEPTOR CAUSES CONFORMATIONAL CHANGES THAT CAUSE RELEASE OF GDP AND BINDING OF GTP

THIS LEADS TO DISASSEMBLY OF SUBUNITS AND FORMATION OF FREE α SUBUNIT AND β - γ COMPLEX . THE α SUBUNIT TRAVELS ALONG THE MEMBRANE AND GOES TO PHOSPHOLIPASE C. PHOSPHOLIPASE C IS A MEMBRANE-BOUND ENZYME A α SUBUNIT ACTIVATES THIS ENZYME.

THE ACTIVE ENZYME THEN INTERACTS WITH PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL 4,5 BISPHOSPHATE OR PIP2 IN SHORT.
NOW, THIS... IS ONE OF THE PHOSPHOLIPIDS FOUND IN THE CELL MEMBRANE.
IT'S MAINLY DISTRIBUTED IN THE INTERNAL LEAFLET OF THE BILAYER

PHOSPHOLIPASE C BREAKS IT DOWN INTO INOSITOL 1,4,5-TRIS-PHOSPHATE OR IN SHORT IP3 AND DIACYLGLYCEROL.

IP3 IS WATER-SOLUBLE SO IT TRAVELS THROUGH THE CYTOSOL AND BINDS TO IP3 RECEPTORS ON THE ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM THIS RECEPTOR IS NOTHING BUT A LIGAND-GATED CA CHANNEL

WE HAVE SEEN IN THIS THE VIDEO ON THE ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM THAT ONE OF THE FUNCTIONS OF THE ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM IS TO STORE CA. THE BINDING OF IP3 TO THIS CA CHANNEL CAUSES OPENING OF THE CHANNEL AND RELEASE OF CA INTO THE CYTOSOL . THE CA THEN BINDS WITH VARIOUS CA BINDING PROTEINS THE MOST IMPORTANT CA BINDING PROTEIN IS CALMODULIN (CAM). ITS BINDING WITH CA PRODUCES CA-CALMODULIN COMPLEX.

NOW THERE ARE MANY ENZYMES IN THE CELL WHOSE ACTIVITY DEPENDS ON THE CA-CALMODULIN COMPLEX.

THEY ARE CALLED CA-CALMODULIN DEPENDENT KINASE OR CAM KINASE.

FOR EXAMPLE, MYOSIN LIGHT CHAIN KINASE IN SMOOTH MUSCLE CELLS IS A CAM KINASE. CA-CALMODULIN COMPLEX ACTIVATES THIS ENZYME CAUSING CONTRACTION OF THE SMOOTH MUSCLE

SO THESE ARE THE EFFECTS DOWNSTREAM IP3 THEN WE ALSO HAVE DAG IN THE MEMBRANE.

IT ACTIVATES PROTEIN KINASE C THIS ONE IS LIKE PKA SEEN IN THE CAMP PATHWAY. IT PHOSPHORYLATES VARIOUS PROTEINS AND MODULATES THEIR ACTIVITY. THIS, IN TURN, PRODUCES A DIFFERENT RESPONSE IN DIFFERENT CELLS.

. OTHER SECOND MESSENGERS ARE DEGRADED.

INOSITOL TRISPHOSPHATE IS DEPHOSPHORYLATED TO INOSITOL WHICH IS

REUTILIZED IN THE SYNTHESIS OF PIP₂. DAG IS CONVERTED TO PHOSPHOLIPIDS.

FINALLY THE CA IS PUMPED BACK INTO THE ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM OR OUT OF THE CELL. SO THIS IS THE PHOSPHOLIPASE C : IP₃ / DAG PATHWAY

Summary

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